

**THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COMMUNICATIVE INTENTION OF
THE SUBJECT OF SPEECH IN A SPECIFIC COMMUNICATION
SITUATION**

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Abstract: *this article is dedicated to considering the role and content of discursive competence in order to teach a foreign language. In it, the author examines the main models of communicative competence of a foreign language, scientific analyzes of discursive competence are presented, and the conceptual content of the terms "discursive competence" and "speech competence" related to communicative competence is deeply researched based on relative scientific approaches.*

Key words: *communicative competence, model, implement, genre, social context.*

A detailed description of the nature and structure of discursive competence requires learning to understand the term “discourse” in linguistics as the basis of the methodology of science.

Many researchers disagree on the historical changes in the meaning of the concept of "discourse". At the present stage, speech is considered as a coherent, communicatively organized speech act, dynamically created and perceived together with extralinguistic factors or speech context. In other words, in addition to the linguistic component - the text, speech also includes an extralinguistic component, which is often considered as a set of the following components: participants in communication, their communicative goals and intentions, pragmatic relationships, social roles, basic knowledge, knowledge about the interlocutor, temporal and spatial conditions of communication.

The linguistic component of speech - text - is understood as a sequence of sentences united by a semantic connection, the main characteristics of which are consistency and integrity. The extralinguistic component of speech - context - "... a communication situation, including the conditions of communication, the scope of the topic, the time and place of communication, the communicants themselves, their attitude to each other, etc." (BFB, 1998). An analysis of the interpretation of this term by domestic and foreign scientists has led to the conclusion that the concept of "extralinguistic context" includes two specific poles - the speaker/writer (subject) and the communicative situation in which speech occurs. In addition, one more component of the extralinguistic context (in addition to the two indicated) should be

highlighted - the type of text (in the same language, the terms "type of communication", "type of communicative action or event" can be used). sense), in this study the term "genre" is defined as follows: Thus, a genre is a type of text that corresponds to the communicative intent of the subject and a specific communicative situation (M. M. Bakhtin, A. Veibitskaya, K. A. Dolinin, V. I. Karasik, M. Yu. Fedosyuk, T. V. Shmeleva, etc.).

Thus, speech, understood by the overwhelming majority of researchers as "text in an extralinguistic context", can be defined in more detail as a certain type of text, i.e. genre, the implementation of the communicative intention of the subject of speech in a specific communication situation (communicative situation). Text in speech, in addition to the real linguistic features (coherence and integrity) realized in it, reflects the features of the implementation of the communicative intention in a given communication situation, which is manifested in the choice of the type of text (genre).) and in a number of text categories, such as addressing, modality, etc.

It seems possible to include the following four components in the concept of speech.

1) Text. This component has a purely linguistic nature, the concept of "text" is considered in a very narrow framework (in contrast to non-text): it is a sequence of sign units united by a semantic connection, the main properties of which are consistency and honesty.

2) Genre. The component has a dual nature, since the choice of purely linguistic features of the text depends on extralinguistic factors - the communicative situation and the subject's intention.

3) Communication status. The extralinguistic factor is one of the aspects of the context, including the temporal and spatial conditions of communication, the social roles and status of the interlocutors, the relationships between them.

4) The subject (speaker/writer) and, above all, his communicative intentions. This extralinguistic component determines the dynamic nature of speech as a purposeful speech process of communication that meets the specific needs and goals of the subject.

5) In accordance with the four components defined in speech (text, genre, communicative situation and speaker/writer, that is, the subject of speech), four components are distinguished in discursive competence.

6) • Textual competence means the ability to organize a sequence of sentences in such a way that they form a single whole - a coherent text with all its properties.

- Genre competence includes knowledge of genre norms and the ability to organize speech in accordance with certain genre laws selected to achieve the communicative goal of the subject in a given context.

- Tactical competence is the ability to analyze a communicative situation and, on this basis, select suitable, adequate and optimal means and methods in a certain language community to achieve the communicative intention of the subject.

- Strategic competence is considered as the ability of the subject to clearly understand his communicative intention and plan a communicative event.

The textual, genre, tactical and strategic components of discursive competence are presented in such a sequence that their correspondence to the structure of speech becomes clearer. If we talk about speech as a process, then the sequence of components should be different, since the initial and determining moment of speech is the communicative intent of the author, and the text is the product and result of speech. Therefore, in the work, the components of discursive competence are considered in the following order: strategic, tactical, genre and textual. It is in this order that they correspond to the process of speech production in real communication.

A detailed study and analysis of each component of discursive competence allows us to characterize it as a set of its structural knowledge and skills for the practical purposes of teaching a foreign language. The following knowledge and skills were defined within the framework of "Discursive Competence" (DC):

- knowing the purpose of one's speech (strategic component of DC);
- implementing general speech planning in accordance with the communicative goal (strategic component of DC);
- analyzing the communicative situation (tactical component of DC);
- determining the communicative intention on this basis and clearly planning one's utterance (tactical component of DC);
- taking into account the parameters of the CC at all stages of speech construction (tactical component of DC);
- selection of the text genre (genre component of the DK);
- compliance with genre laws (genre component of the DK);
- presentation of information in the form of a hierarchy of semantic predicates (text component of the DK);
- reflection of this hierarchy in the structure of parts of the text (text component of the DK);
- unification of individual parts into a whole using various groups of integrity properties (text component of the DK);

- organize a coherent sequence of sentences using lexical and grammatical means at the level of a text segment and the entire text (text component of the DK).

Research in the field of linguistics, psycholinguistics and psychology show that there are significant differences between oral and written speech. Analysis of these works made it possible to describe the specific features of the activity of discursive competence in written speech.

At the level of strategic competence, it is necessary to talk about such features as preliminary preparation, awareness, motivation and arbitrariness of the written form of speech.

The first two features indicate that expressive writing as its most important stage includes the stage of internal reflection, planning and programming of the statement. If we talk about oral speech, its strategic nature can be questioned, since it is not always thought out in advance, the communicative intent is often not fully realized by the author of the statement, for written speech this feature is fundamental, he specifies. and many other of its unique features. The specific feature of the motivational field of written speech is associated with the absence of the addressee in the process of speech production, the discrepancy between the state of writing the text and the state of communication. And if in oral speech the motivation for communication often comes from the communication situation itself, then written communication is always voluntary. Thus, the share of strategic competence in written speech is significantly higher than in oral speech. Tactical competence includes clarification of the communicative behavior of the subject aimed at achieving the communicative goal, as well as the achievement of secondary goals, taking into account the parameters of the communicative situation. The specificity of the activity of tactical competence in oral and written speech is explained, first of all, by the difference in the communicative situation of the two nominal forms of speech. Since in written communication the situation of direct communication is absent, it is necessary to clearly express such parameters as the image of the author and the image of the addressee, which are reflected in the categories of address and modality. The attribution of these categories to the characteristics of written speech does not mean that they are absent in oral speech. Addressability and modality are important features of oral and written speech, but the complexity of their expression in written texts requires special attention to them in the educational process.

Genre competence in oral and written speech is distinguished, first of all, by a specific set of genres in each form of speech. The main differences between the genres of written and oral speech are that, firstly, most of them relate to the sphere of

formal communication; secondly, they are completely canonized. For these reasons, the importance of genre competence in written speech is especially great.

In the process of speech production, the absence of an addressee and the state of direct communication also determine the uniqueness of text competence in written speech. Detail, consistency, consistency, integrity, completeness - all the features inherent in the text are primarily associated with the written text due to the need for preliminary preparation, processing and maximum accuracy and completeness of text information.

The selected characteristics allow us to conclude that it is important and necessary to take into account the features of each form of speech in the process of developing discursive competence.

In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, two ways of developing different types of competencies are possible: one involves a gradual transition from reproductive exercises to productive ones, and the other - direct training in speech activity. The proposed methodology is based on the reproductive-productive model, which requires taking into account the optimal balance between the reproductive and productive components when creating a written speech work in a foreign language and, as a consequence, when developing discursive competence. .

The solution to the issue of the role of proliferation in the formation of DK is a matter of content and form. It is well known that imperfect mastery of form complicates the presentation of content and slows down the creation of a text. In this regard, at the level of the content plan, we believe that it is necessary to teach students reproduction with elements of production (expressing their thoughts), reproduction (transmitting content) and creativity (assessment, personal attitude, etc.).).).

Regarding the form of a written statement, it is recommended to talk about giving priority to the reproductive and productive nature of the design of the content, which depends on the following factors:

1. Knowledge of a foreign language (even at the highest level) is based on an increase in a significant number of combinations of words, phrases, cliches, etc. Otherwise, the interference of the native language leads to contextual, situational or habitual misuse of language units.

2. Language at all levels is characterized by a large number of cases of stereotyping. Canonization of many genres of written and (less often) oral speech requires special attention, which presupposes the obligatory repetition of their

rhetorical, stylistic, structural, compositional, lexical and grammatical features when creating individual types of texts.

Thus, in the field of expressive writing, the task of the teacher is to teach students to creatively use ready-made and independently constructed language units and constructions to express their thoughts or convey information contained in the main text (prototype).

References:

1. Speech Genres and Other Late Essays presents six short works from Bakhtin's Aesthetics of Creative Discourse, published in Moscow in 1979
2. The problem of speech genres 45 years after Bakhtin's article // Russian Studies: Linguistic paradigm of the end of the 20th century. - St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg State University Publishing House, 1998. - P. 35-46.
3. "Questionnaire of a Speech Genre" of T. V. Shmeleva: Past, Present, Future (for the 30th Anniversary of the Genre Model)
4. Linguistic and communicative circle, key, matrix: on the significance of V. I. Karasik's ideas for communicative linguistics
5. Maksetova N., Uteshova Z. LINGUISTIC PROBLEMS OF ENGLISH LEXICOGRAPHY //Journal of Universal Science Research. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 1099-1108.